

**LINGUACULTURAL ASPECT OF TOPONYMS IN ENGLISH DISCOURSE (ON THE
BASIS OF NOVEL "NEVER LET ME GO" BY KAZUO ISHIGURO)**

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Abstract. The article discusses the functioning of toponyms in the work "Never let me go" by Kazuo Ishiguro. The primary attention is paid to the study of the narrative and ideological relation between the semantic and etymological meanings of toponyms in the novel. Moreover, the focus is on studying the origin of them and their expressive features. Especially, linguistic and cultural and historical features are taken as the main object in the article. The article deals with the research of toponyms as Hailsham, Norfolk, appellatives nominating locations in the function of the toponyms (Cottages, Gallery).

Keywords: proper nouns, toponyms, oikodomens, Hailsham, Ishiguro, Norfolk, Cottages, Gallery, completion.

Introduction. Kazuo Ishiguro is considered as one of the most famous contemporary writers and his dystopian novel "Never let me go" [1] is definitely a masterpiece of its genre. "Never Let Me Go" is a 2005 science fiction novel by the British author Kazuo Ishiguro. It was shortlisted for the 2005 Man Booker Prize (an award Ishiguro had previously won in 1989 for *The Remains of the Day*), for the 2006 Arthur C. Clarke Award and for the 2005 National Book Critics Circle Award. Time magazine named it the best novel of 2005 and included the novel in its "100 Best English-language novels published since 1923—the beginning of TIME". [2]

There are a lot of researches and works done on the basis of the analysis of different aspects of the novel. Virginia Yeung investigates how the situation reflects human beings' confrontation with mortality. She gave an emphasis on the link between mortality and memory, which is posited as a function of the mind that can help assuage the psychic trauma of mortality in the story [3]. Louis Menand in his article "Something about Kathy" discusses the issue of the triangle (Kathy, Ruth, Tommy) and the features of their characters, he dealt with the plot and its correlation with the main characters' behaviour. [4] On the other hand, Gabrielle Grrifin viewed to the problem of indicating genre of the novel and argued whether "Never let me go" should be considered as related to the science or cultural work. [5] As we can see, various authors suggests different points of view and tried to analyze the work deeply, in turn, in this article we intend to make the analysis of proper nouns used by Kazuo Ishiguro as carers of meaning, by understanding linguistic and cultural features of chosen toponyms.

It is obvious that, the writer was very scrupulous with every detail in the work as well as with onomastic units he intentionally selected for the characters and places in the novel according to the meanings they bear. Proper nouns in the work serve to establish a distinct and nuanced setting. The use of specific names for locations, institutions, and characters contributes to the novel's dystopian atmosphere, emphasizing the isolation of the characters in their unique reality.

Through the employment of proper nouns, Ishiguro creates a world that is simultaneously familiar and unsettling, inviting readers to reflect on the implications of the society depicted in the novel. The careful selection and placement of these names play a crucial role in shaping the narrative and enhancing the overall thematic depth of the story. In "Never Let Me Go" proper nouns play a crucial role in establishing the setting, characterizing individuals, and contributing to the overall atmosphere of the novel.

The careful use of proper nouns in the work contributes to the novel's exploration of identity, memory, and the ethical implications of science and technology. The names of places and roles serve to anchor the narrative in a distinct world while also carrying symbolic weight within the story's context.

Toponyms: Hailsham. The choice of names in literature is often symbolic, and Ishiguro likely selected "Hailsham" to enhance the thematic elements of his novel, creating a memorable and evocative backdrop for the characters' experiences. "Hailsham stood in a smooth hollow with fields rising on all sides. That meant that from almost any of the classroom windows in the main house—and even from the pavilion—you had a good view of the long narrow road that came down across the fields and arrived at the main gate. The gate itself was still a fair distance off, and any vehicle would then have to take the gravelled drive, going past shrubs and flowerbeds, before at last reaching the courtyard in front of the main house. Days could sometimes go by without us seeing a vehicle coming down that narrow road, and the ones that did were usually vans or lorries bringing supplies, gardeners or workmen. A car was a rarity, and the sight of one in the distance was sometimes enough to cause bedlam during a class." [1] Kazuo Ishiguro chose the name "Hailsham" for the fictional boarding school in his novel "Never Let Me Go" deliberately. The name is intended to evoke a sense of Englishness and small-town familiarity. It contributes to the atmosphere of the story and the illusion of a seemingly ordinary and idyllic setting that conceals darker truths. According to its origin, Hailsham is a market town in East Sussex, England. Its name is believed to have Saxon origins, possibly derived from "Haegel's Ham," meaning Hail's settlement. The town has a rich history dating back to medieval times. Kazuo Ishiguro chose the name "Hailsham" for the fictional boarding school in his novel "Never Let Me Go" to create a sense of nostalgia and a seemingly ordinary English setting. The choice of a familiar place name contrasts with the unsettling nature of the story, adding to the overall atmosphere of the novel. The juxtaposition of the mundane and the extraordinary serves to enhance the impact of the dystopian themes explored in the narrative.

Toponyms. Norfolk. We come across with another geographical name in the book: Norfolk. The writer has not randomly chosen this name. Norfolk in England is a county located in East Anglia. It is known for its scenic landscapes, historic towns, and the Norfolk Broads, a network of rivers and lakes. Kazuo Ishiguro chose Norfolk as a setting for his work, because of its serene and isolated atmosphere. The rural landscapes provide a backdrop that enhances the contemplative and reflective themes in his novel. "You see, because [Norfolk is] stuck out here on the east, on this hump jutting into the sea, it's not on the way to anywhere. People going north and south, they bypass it altogether. For that reason, it's a peaceful corner of England, rather nice. But it's also something of a lost corner... Someone claimed after the lesson that Miss Emily had said Norfolk was England's 'lost corner' because that was were all the lost property found in the country ended up." [1]

Toponyms. (oikodomonym) Cottages. The Cottages, located in Norfolk, is a farm where

the characters live after leaving Hailsham. The name "Cottages" evokes a sense of simplicity, rural life, and communal living. It signifies a departure from the structured and sheltered environment of Hailsham, as the characters begin to forge their own paths and confront the inevitability of their fate. The Cottages represent a stage of transition and self-discovery for the characters.

Toponyms. (oikodomonym) The Gallery. The "Gallery" is a location within the novel where the characters visit during their time at Hailsham, the boarding school where they are raised.

In the context of the novel, "The Gallery" refers to a room or space where the students' artwork and other creative endeavors are displayed and appreciated. It serves as a setting for the characters to showcase their artistic expressions and engage with their own creativity. "The Gallery" holds cultural significance within the confines of Hailsham by nurturing the students' artistic talents and providing them with a sense of identity and purpose.

The presence of "The Gallery" underscores the themes of art, creativity, and self-expression that permeate throughout the novel, as well as the characters' desire to explore their own humanity despite their unique circumstances as clones.

Kazuo Ishiguro leads his reader throughout the narrative gradually alternating the location of the story, which includes reminiscences of the main character "Never let me go", in turn we can identify these stages as followings:

1. **Hailsham:** The initial stage is set at Hailsham, a boarding school where the main characters, including Kathy, Ruth, and Tommy, grow up. This section establishes the unique environment, relationships, and the mysterious nature of the characters' existence. It introduces the themes of friendship, love, and the inevitability of their predetermined fates as clones raised for organ donations.

2. **Cottages:** The narrative transitions to the Cottages, a more adult setting where the characters confront the reality of their purpose as organ donors. This stage delves deeper into the characters' relationships, the impact of their short life expectancies, and their attempts to find meaning and connections.

3. **Completion:** The final stage focuses on the characters as they approach "completion," the term used for reaching the end of their organ donation cycles. This part of the narrative explores acceptance, reflection, and the characters' attempts to make sense of their lives and relationships in the face of their impending fate.

These three stages structure the novel and contribute to its exploration of themes such as identity, mortality, and the ethical implications of human cloning.

Conclusion. Proper nouns in literary works as we delved into analysis of Kazuo Ishiguro's work "Never let me go" serve several functions. They can:

1. **Establish Setting:** Proper nouns, such as names of cities, countries, or specific locations, help establish the setting of the story. They provide a concrete sense of place for the reader. (Hailsham, Norfolk, Cottages, Gallery)

2. **Create Atmosphere:** Proper nouns can contribute to the atmosphere or mood of a story. For example, a majestic mountain or a bustling city may evoke different emotions. Author used reminisces of the heroine to depict comparison among various locations of characters and the changes that occurred to them each time the background setting was alternated.

3. **Characterization:** Names of characters, often proper nouns, can carry significance and contribute to the characterization. The choice of names might convey cultural, historical, or symbolic meanings. Kazuo Ishiguro masterfully made use of implicatures when he named his

characters with names etymologically emerged in biblical times, not to mention that he used different cognomens to convey the characters' distinguishing features and the atmosphere of the plot.

4. Symbolism: Proper nouns can be used symbolically to represent abstract concepts, ideologies, or historical events, adding depth to the narrative, like the functions of the appellatives Donors and Guardians, which divide the individuals within narrative not on the nations, ethnic groups, but classes, separating "people" and "clones".

5. Plot Development: Specific places, events, or objects identified by proper nouns can be integral to the plot, acting as points of conflict, resolution, or transformation. As we mentioned above, the novel went through three stages advancing to the culmination and settings were changed three times as well.

6. Authenticity: Using actual names of places or people lends authenticity to the narrative, especially in historical fiction or works grounded in real-world settings. Even though the author created alternative science-fiction dystopian novel, he called his characters with real names, which can be considered as modern, he did purposefully, in order to dive readers into the thoughts of possible reality.

7. Theme Reinforcement: Proper nouns can reinforce or underscore central themes of a literary work. For instance, a town's name might reflect the overall theme of the story. In this case, the name of boarding school remained as major in the whole story, so that its name "Hailsham" manifested as phenomena.

Overall, the inclusion of proper nouns contributes to the richness and depth of a literary work by providing specificity, context, and layers of meaning.

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